

KSZTAŁTOWANIE LEKSYKI MŁODSZYCH UCZNIÓW NA LEKCJACH JEZYKA UKRAIŃKIEGO

Siranczuk Natalia

doktor nauk pedagogicznych, profesor, kierownik wydziału teorii i metod kształcenia szkół podstawowych Równego Państwowego Humanistycznego Uniwersytetu, Równe, Ukraina,

Artykuł ujawnia istotę kompleksowego metodycznego systemu kształtowania kompetencji leksykalnych u uczniów szkół podstawowych na lekcjach języka ukraińskiego; stoi metodologiczną zasadę tworzenia słownictwa młodszych uczniów, którego istota polega na kształtowanie zawartości i materiałów dydaktycznych ukierunkowanych na różnych etapach kształcenia, ze stopniowym wzrostem ilości informacji językowej zgłoszonych na dany temat, złożoność jego charakteru i formy prezentacji; krótko opisuje system multi-stopniowanie ćwiczeń z utworzeniem struktury leksykalnej nadawania w ich pracy dla uczniów językowych ustnych i pisemnych; opisuje wybór zgodnie z metodologicznymi zasadami i kryteriami materiału dydaktycznego.

Artykuł wyjaśnia, że czwarto klasistów nadal aktywnie uczą się standardowych modeli konstruowania spójnego tekstu: uczniowie uczą się systemu łączności (powtórzeń zaimka), składnia staje się bardziej skomplikowana.

Uczniów o wysokim poziomie rozwoju intelektualnego wyprzedzają swoich rówieśników w tworzeniu systemu wzajemnych połączeń jednostek leksykonu. W opowieściach o intelektualnie uzdolnionych dzieciach istnieje «dorosły» poziom rozwoju słownika.

Warianty indywidualne, czyli odchylenia od norm i stereotypów wieku przejawia się przede wszystkim różnorodności w tekstach leksykalnych, składniowej złożoności, właściwego wykorzystania środków łączności. Naturalnie takie teksty są często tworzone przez intelektualnie uzdolnione dzieci, które uczą się w ramach programu eksperymentalnego.

Badanie układ doświadczalny jest katalizatorem tworzenia tekstowych kompetencji uczniów przejawia się przede wszystkim w bogactwie i systemowego słownictwa. Znaczące różnice w kompetencjach tekstowych uczniów szkolonych w systemach tradycyjnych i eksperymentalnych są wykrywane u chłopców. Oznacza to, że chłopcy są ważniejsi niż dziewczęta, których się systemy nauki.

W pracach czwartoklasistów zauważalna formacja symbolicznej reprezentacji mowy, gdy uczeń celowo pracuje nad technikami mowy, udoskonala formę realizacji własnych intencji mowy. Jednak w wieku dziesięciu lat tylko inteligentnie uzdolnieni dzieci, uczące programy rozwojowe, spontanicznie wypowiadają przemówienia.

W tekstach uczniów szkół podstawowych praktycznie nie ma świadomej pracy nad słowem, świadomego wyboru przenośnych środków. Kreatywność przejawia się nie w pracy językowego materiału tekstu, ale w rozwoju fabuły, indywidualizacji bohaterów. Daje to podstawy do stwierdzenia, że kompetencje leksykalne dzieci wynikają przede wszystkim z makrostruktury, a nie z mikrostruktury tekstu. Do rozwoju makrostruktury niezbędne są następujące operacje intelektualne: analiza, kombinacja, tłumaczenie reprezentacji mentalnych z kodu graficznego na słowny. Właśnie dlatego leksykalna kompetencja młodszego ucznia wiąże się z wysokim poziomem rozwoju intelektualnego, treningiem w programach eksperymentalnych.

Słowa kluczowe: kompetencje leksykalne uczniów szkół podstawowych, kształtowanie kompetencji leksykalnych uczniów szkół podstawowych, całościowa metoda kształtowania kompetencji leksykalnych uczniów szkoły podstawowej, zajęcia językowe zorientowane na kompetencje, metody interpretowania słów, system ćwiczeń według poziomów gradacji metodologicznej.

THE FORMATION OF THE LEXICAL COMPETENCE OF JUNIOR PUPILS AT LESSONS OF THE UKRAINIAN LANGUAGE

Siranchuk Nataliia

doctor of pedagogical sciences, professor, head of the department of the theory and methods of elementary education of Rivne State Humanitarian University, Rivne, Ukraine,

The article deals with the process of forming Junior pupils' lexical competency in the structure of the speech theory activity. The most effective principles of the method of forming lexical competence on a functional basis are determined .

In primary classes the girls' lexical competence is bigger than the boys' one. There are some indicators which established the level of speaking development and creative abilities in primary classes. They are: phonetical, lexically-semantic, syntactic and stylistic devices; stylistic figures: rhetorical questions on the elements of intonation expression. We can't separate these indicators from general communicative competency.

The lexical competence depends on the environmental influence and as for this competence the potentialities are socially conditioned.

Therefore, lexical competence are related to the special and intellectual abilities which person's individual-psychological peculiarities, which are the conditions for successful realization of speaking and creative action.

Key words: the lexical competence of junior pupils, the formation of the lexical competence of junior pupils, the comprehensive methodological system formation of the lexical competence of junior pupils, competency-oriented the lessons of speech, the methods for interpretation of words, the methodological multilevel gradual an exercise system.

Introduction. The problem of developing speaking and creative abilities has attracted many scientists. Despite this is was the research of O. Amatewa, B. Belkina, A. Bogush, N. Vetlygina, N. Gawrush , O. Dronowa, T. Komarowa, T. Korahowa, N. Sakyliina, O. Ysharowa, N. Fesuhowa, N. Yagupkova and others.

To better understand the lexical competence, we've carried out market research with more than 1000 teachers in the Ukraine. Over half of those surveyed reported that at least 70% of their pupils lacked the vocabulary needed to access their learning. Worryingly, 93% of primary school teachers believe lacked the vocabulary is increasing.

In schools, language underpins progress, impacts on attainment throughout primary and secondary years, affects self-esteem and behaviour and plays a huge role in a child's future life chances. Without enough language – the lexical competence – a child is seriously limited in their enjoyment of school and success beyond.

On analysis of linguistic, psycholinguistic and methodological literature, was found that a lexical competence is ability of personality quickly and qualitatively, at the level of the program to operate not words, but semantic fields, from composition of that a pupils elects a necessary word, word-combination, that with exactness to express own opinion in the process of communication.

We mean formation of the lexical competence of junior pupils – that correct organization of motivational, cognitive, practical, reflexive lexical activity, which are based on rules and peculiarities of grammatical structure of language, using of the sufficient number words supply within the limits of age-old period, adequate using of lexemes, appropriate using of expressive means – expressions of figurativeness, proverbs, epithets, idioms.

The lexical competence of junior pupils is one of integrating quality of personality of student that allows consciously and creatively to determine and carry out own life,

develop the individuality, arrive at successful, optimal vital functions. Provided successful implementation of the methods of studies in elementary school described of the activities, the lexical competence of junior pupils will grow and the results of educational activity of schoolchildren to create an environment for identifying among them linguistically gifted children, which able to handle a lot of languages at the same time. The pupils would be able on the base to operate semantic fields of the native language in parallel learn to the semantic fields of the other languages, for example, Polish, Russian, English etc. Evidently that the pupils what can achieve of the lexical competence Polish, Russian, English etc.

The optimal solution to the problems of competency-oriented studies and speech development of junior pupils was possible if there was methodical educational system what satisfies present scientific knowledge about a language and speech. Experimental educational system was reflecting pattern the acquisition of language according to principles of studies. Relationship between language and speech learning; graduation who had said in accelerate the pace of speech development by improving speech creative system; lexical fund and grammatical structure building and the relationship between them; relationship development among phonetic, lexical, grammatical side of speech and language learning; comparison and differentiated linguistic unit in the process speech activities were among them.

Basic methodological principle formation of the lexical competence junior pupils is graduation. This principle is about for structuring content of teaching and didactics material according to established themes and focused at the different stages of learning. This principle invokes a gradual expanding and increasingly complex linguistic information to established themes.

The scientific novelty of researches is approving according to what was creating for the first time a comprehensive methodological system formation of the lexical competence of junior pupils at lessons of the Ukrainian language, scientific justification and clarified principles and methods of speech development of pupils, found that basic methodological principle formation of the lexical competence junior pupils is graduation. This principle is about for structuring content of teaching and didactics material according to established themes and focused at the different stages of learning. This principle invokes a gradual expanding and increasingly complex linguistic information to established themes. A multilevel gradual an exercise system that promotes development lexical fund and grammatical structure and the relationship between them was creating. New didactic support materials were chosen and structured an according to methodological principles and criteria (*Siranchuk, 2017, p.13*). The typology and structure of competency-oriented the lessons of Ukrainian speech were introduced in education in practice. Comprehension and analysis of text of the specimen were main activity in experimental learning. A result of learning was produced own spoken and written utterances.

The practical value of scientific research lies in the possibility to use research finding in the process of improving school Ukrainian curriculum, school textbooks, didactic material and the preparation a special subject at education science faculties with a degree primary education. The framework paper form of text that contributes to the enhancement teachers' performance and results and include clearer guidelines on lexical work, which takes into account types of text, the content of the text, the intention of the text, expressive means it was suggested. The scheme for the analysis creative work of

the pupils and matrices of text (retelling or composition) for the diagnostics levels of different sides of the lexical structure of the Ukrainian language to which had been developed key for the standardization diagnostic of the results was elaborated and present. The final quiz to estimate understanding of the basic lexical terms, the levels of use of the basic lexical terms, the various lexical skills according to allocating curricular mandates about speech skills and ability were developed and implemented into practice primary education. There was justified of requires the existence and use study notebooks which, on account of their content and methodological guidance correspond to intention and tasks about formation of the lexical competence of junior pupils at lessons of the Ukrainian language. There was creating of the text card indices what includes of revised and not revised training texts, accompanied by the methodological paper forms. Selected linguistic material classified according to themes and style of speech. The material was valuable training tools, by means of which the teacher can choose of the text, what is in line with the didactic principles and specific tasks of lesson.

Nowadays, the most actual problem of children's language research is to identify the individual strategies about the speech behavior and «the entrance in the language». It means that the main object of the research – is not the general laws which have been already set by linguistics and psycholinguistics, but the variability of their manifestations in children of different sexes, pupils (developing) who are enrolled in different systems and in children with different cognitive and psychological characteristics.

This formulation of the problem allows us to look different at a full monologic utterance, «writing» of the child. The construction of full monologic utterance, including a coherent text, can be seen as a manifestation of the child's personality, a more or less consciousness (innate) of breakeing the existing and already mastered standard. Indeed, in the generation of expanded verbal expression it is need not only to operate the grammatical structures and vocabulary units, but also to create «Closed semantic system»: to organize the plan, build the order of the themes. It means that in the conscious the macrostructure is practiced (plot, predicate hierarchy) with the microstructure (actually the embodiment of language) of the text (about macro- and microstructure of the text). It is clear that, the construction of a «closed system of meaning» and adequate realization it into speech – a difficult task for an adult speaker: but not all adults have a full text competence. The more difficult it is for the child, whose language competence and the level of cognitive development are noticeably different from the adults ones.

Let us look for speech analysis of coherent monologic speech of a ten year child on the writing material. Let's try to identify the standard of a narrative strategy and its individual variation in children, it depends on the biological (sex) and social (training by the traditional or experimental program) and psychological (the level of intellectual development) factors. The study was conducted on the material of fairy tales on the theme «Forest». Subject Selection is not accidental.

Keyword "Forest" has an average associative strength, often occurs as a reaction to the most different incentives, takes 54th place in the dictionary of the subjective frequency, and «almost often than not». «Forest» refers to the core of the internal lexicon (but not to the center of the core), this word is connected with the mastered cognitive space which formes in the urban child more on the basis of cultural artifacts than on their own experience.

Material was obtained from the pupils of the third forms. The schools locate in

Rivne (Ukraine): the special language experimental class and ordinary class of the secondary school. Pupils of the experimental class are intellectually gifted children, who are selected by the psychologist. Thus, factors of the educational system and the level of intelligence is not specifically separated. There are selected texts from the detailed analysis of 36 texts which match the requirements of the genre (compositions about forest descriptions in different seasons and stories about a hike in the forest are excluded from the material, also they are deprived from fantastic episodes).

Methods of the material analysis: semantic analysis, structural analysis, associative techniques, statistical methods (correlation analysis - CA, dispersive analysis - DA).

Researching parameters: the lexical component of the language ability; syntactic component of the language ability; textual competence.

The estimations of the lexical components are:

1 – the coefficient of the text covering with the associative field of the word FOREST (the number of associations to the word Forest to the total number of the lexemes in the text). Coefficient of a text which is covered by the children's association with the word Forest depicts the measure of stereotyped text: the more coincidences with the associative field, the greater focus on the standard situation and speech cliches in the generation of the text. The text's vocabulary was compared with the children's associations.

The relation of the number of tokens, which coincide with the children's associations of vocabulary, to the total number of tokens in the text and it is conditionally denoted as C_{da} , the covering coefficient of the text by children associative field. Beside this, the vocabulary of fairy tales was compared with the adults' associations, "standard" (Karaylov and others., 1994). The relation of the tokens number, which matches to the associations of adults' vocabulary to the total number of tokens in the text conditionally denotes C_{sa} , the coefficient of a text which is covered by an adult (standart) associative field. A comparison with the children associations allow us to denote: the formation of age norms according to the lexical component of the speaking ability, comparison with the adults – proximity to the "standart" adults' norm

2 – coefficient of a text's lexical diversity C_{lex} (the relation of the number of different tokens to the total number of tokens). Coefficient of a lexical diversity reflects the wealth of vocabulary, which was manifested in composing stories. The higher coefficient is, the more vocabulary of the tales varies, and also there is more richness of vocabulary in the text creation.

1 – coefficient of the syntactic complexity C_{synt} (the relation of number of the simple sentences, which are complicated with homogeneous members, adverbs and gerund to the total number of the simple sentences in the text). The higher the coefficient is, the more frequently we may find homogeneous members, adverbs, and the more complex syntax is in the text;

2 – the coefficient of the pronominalization $C_{pronouns}$ (the relation of amount of the word forms to the total number of word usage). The coefficient of pronominalization allows us to indicate the formation of differentiation between deictic and nominative vocabulary units, and the specifics of their operation in the expanded text, in particular, the role of the deictic units in text coherence. The higher value of the coefficient is, the more frequently we may find pronoun in the text and also the less accurate the nomination and more flawed the semantic connectivity of the text.

After calculating of the coefficients, the quantitative data was processed by the variance analysis. The purpose of using DA: is to identify which factor has bigger affect on the level of the manifestation of the lexical and syntactic competence in the textual activity: gender, the systeme of education. With the variance analysis we considered some resulting facts as: the lexical component of a language ability; the syntactic component of a language ability. *Table 1* shows the results of DA material.

Consider the data which is presented in a *Table 1*. The meanings of the criterion of the truthfulness, exceed the standard, are underlined. In any case when the meaning of the criterion of the truthfulness exceeds the standard value, obtained from our material laws can be extended to the entire amount. It means that not only in the examined cases, but also in all others the factors and the system of education make an impact on the indicators of a lexical competence as covering adults (standart) and children associative field and also on the syntactic competence (using of the pronouns and the syntactic complexity). We comment the results that can be spread on the entire population.

Table 1.

For fairytales: the indicators of the influence (η^2) and the criterions of truthfulness

(F standard = 8,5 when $P > 0,99$; 4,5 when $P > 0,95$)

Factor	C_{da}		C_{sa}		C_{lex}		$C_{pronouns}$		C_{synt}	
	η^2	F	η^2	F	η^2	F	η^2	F	η^2	F
The system of education	0	0	8,3	19,3	0,1	0	0	0	0,1	0,4
Sex	0	0	0	0	0,1	0	3,7	8,5	4,3	78,0
The combination of factors	0,5	15,8	0,7	1,3	0,1	0,1	1,3	3,0	4,2	73,9

Let's start with the lexical component of the language competence.

When we cover a text with children's associations, combination of factors, gender and the system of education influence on it. For both boys and girls who are enrolled in the traditional system, it is more common to find associative field to the word FOREST in the fairytales than their peers who are enrolled in the experimental system. In the girls' texts there are more coincidences with the children's field of associations than in the boys' ones, average value of C_{da} 0.24 and 0.21. There are the least amount of children's associations coincidences in the girls' texts who are in the experimental class. It means that girls' texts from the regular class and regular school are focused on children (age) norms. In these texts are explicated the age stereotypes; on the contrary texts of intellectually gifted girls reflect age norms and stereotypes at the least form.

Factor of the learning system influences on text with the adults' associations. In children's texts who are enrolled in the experimental program, we can see many associations from the «adult» associative field. Adults' association are common for both boys and girls. It means that children who are enrolled in the experimental system, orient on adults' level of forming speaking competence according to the lexical component in their textual activity. In their tales we can meet age stereotypes and clichés.

According to the received information the lexical diversity of the text partly depends on the sex and the system of education. More precisely, the dependence of sex and the system of education can be seen in our material, but the degree of influence of

two factors on the lexical diversity is small. We can say that according to the childrens' tendency who are enrolled in the experimental system, there are more diverse with the vocabulary in their texts than children who are enrolled in the traditional system. At the same time the boys show a greater wealth of vocabulary than girls (average values C_{lex} 0.71 and 0.67).

Let us Consider the indicators of the syntactic component of the language competence.

The child's sex influences on the pronouns' number in the text. Number of pronouns in the girls' texts is much less than in the boys' texts. It means that girls have better imagine about different functions of nominative and deictic units in the connected speech then boys have. At the same time the girls who are enrolled in the experimental system, go a little ahead then their peers who are enrolled in the traditional system (a combination of factors is evaluated by the stage of influence 1.3).

The child's sex affects on the syntactic complexity, and in the connection with the system of education. There are more simple sentences, participles and verbal participle phrases in boys' texts from the experimental class. However, the differences according to this indicator between boys and girls from the experimental class is much more noticeable (an average values C_{synt} 0.72 and 0.51) than between boys and girls from the regular class (an average values C_{synt} 0.47 and 0.56). It means that the most difficult text's syntax is in the boys' texts who are enrolled in the experimental system, and the most simple – in the children's ones who are enrolled in the traditional system, especially in boys.

There are some **conclusions** which is based on the analysis of the material:

1. Important theoretical contributions was enacting in didactics Ukrainian language two methods formation of the lexical competence junior pupils – onosemasyological and semantic. With these methods as a basis were outlined some training tools to interpret the words, such as demonstration, contextual, logical, descriptive, synonymous-antonymous and structural-semantic.

Implementation of this educational system formation of the lexical competence junior pupils can occur not only at traditional lessons what basic grammar of the Ukrainian and literacy skills, but special competency-oriented the lessons of speech. The typology and peculiarity of these lessons defined under the research process. The thematic planning and lesson notes from some teachers described in the thesis.

2. There is an active exploration of the standard models according for building the connected texts in age 9 - 10 years: children learn a system of connected means (pronominal repetitions), the syntax is complicated. The learning strategy of building connected text for boys and girls is uneven: the boys quickly learn complex syntax, girls - system of connected tools.

3. Children with a high level of intelligence outgo their peers in the formation of the system of interrelations vocabulary units. In fairy tales of gifted children "adult" level of vocabulary.

4. Individual variability and the derogation from the age norms and stereotypes, manifest in the lexical texts, greater syntactic complexity and the proper use of means of connectivity. Intellectually gifted children often create such texts who are enrolled in the experimental program.

5. Education on the experimental system is a catalyst for the formation of child's text competencies, which is manifested primarily in the richness and systematic of the

vocabulary. There are large differences in the textual competence of children who are enrolled in the traditional and experimental systems especially we can see it in boys. Ego means that for boys is more important that system by which they are trained than for girls.

6. Individual variation is fully manifested in children with a high level of intelligence. To a greater extent this dependence is typical for boys than for girls.

There is no conscious work on the word from texts of the nine- and ten-years children and the conscious choice of figurative means. Creativity is manifested not only in work on the linguistic side of the text, but in the plot development and on the individualization of the characters. It leads to the conclusion that children's linguistic creativity is primarily due to macrostructure, but not to the microstructure of text. For the development of macrostructure we need such intellectual operations as analytism, combination and the transfer of the mental representations from the figurative code to verbal. That is why linguistic creativity is associated with a high level of the intellectual development, and is trained according to the developing and experimental programs.

Competency-oriented the lessons of speech is characterizing by the purpose, content and technology for giving instruction together with specificities relationship between teacher and pupils. In the thesis is justified typology of competency-oriented the lessons of Ukrainian speech, which aims to formation of the lexical competence of primary school pupils. That typology opens the door for put into practice of the purpose, content and principles for training pupils with adequate methods and training tools.

An important means of lexical competence formation of junior pupils is organized the work for the errors prevention. The work is carried out in an orderly classification for the speech errors with the advent of theirs nomenclature a specific kind of lexical errors, which often related to the lack of knowledge of the lexical meaning of the word. We term this type of errors orfonymic (Siranchuk, 2017, p.97).

The formative and educational potential of the proposed methodological system provides not only formation of language skills and linguistic knowledge for junior pupils, their communication competence, language ability, but also development of their creative abilities, high moral standing and personal integrity.

The system of lexical concepts laid on the base of learning content on the competency-oriented classes – a system of theoretical knowledge about language, its forms, types and properties. Introduction of practical, cognitive and speaking tasks to the content – is the another feature of competence-oriented speaking lesson (Siranchuk, 2017, p.463). These exercises consist cognitive questions what reveal the subject of a lesson. Solving of the practical problems according to the speaking situation promotes cognitive needs of pupils, creates their positive motivation for verbal skills, and provides a conscious learning. The lack of rules in the traditional sense, system replacement of questions and tasks, algorithms and tokens allows child to do the independent conclusions and generalizations. The majority of searching and creative exercises help to enhance mental and speaking activity of pupils.

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